

How Neuroscience and Emotional Identification Shape Consumer Psychology

Siwoo Choi

GEMS Dubai American Academy

Mr Craig Stuart Conlon

March/4/2026

1425 Words

Abstract

In this modern world, companies' marketing teams have shifted from observing external consumer behaviours to analysing internal neurological triggers, trying to maximise the consumers' brain chemistry and years of evolution. This paper explores the integration of neuroscience; especially the roles of the prefrontal cortex and the limbic system: the behavioural and emotional brain structures, with the emotional identification strategies in contemporary marketing. By examining how brands utilize mirror neurons and dopamine pathways, the research demonstrates that purchasing decisions are often the result of subconscious emotional resonance rather than rational utility. The findings suggest that emotional identification acts as a primary driver in brand loyalty, effectively bypassing the prefrontal cortex which controls the consumers' logic, and influencing long-term consumer habits.

Keywords: Neuromarketing, Limbic System, Prefrontal cortex, Mirror Neurons, Somatic Markers, Electroencephalography (EEG), functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI)

Case Studies: Neurological Principles in Action

The theoretical framework linking neuroscience to consumer behaviour gains its most compelling support from real-life brand applications. For my research, I have used three widely studied cases: Coca-Cola, Nike, and the Starbucks Rewards Program. These three case studies reveal and illustrate how the limbic system, mirror neurons, and dopamine pathways operate not as just concepts, but as practical drivers in modern marketing strategy.

Some of the most cited neurological case study in marketing literature is the Coca-Cola versus Pepsi blind-taste experiment. Morin (2011) reported that when participants were unaware of which beverage they were consuming, they reported a preference towards Pepsi, with activity concentrated in an older limbic structure tied towards instinctual and emotional behaviour. However, when participants knew they were drinking Coke, they stated a preference towards Coke, and the brain region that lit up shifted to the prefrontal cortex, which is a specific region that is linked to brand memory, identity, and cultural meaning. This neurological reversal reveals that what consumers are purchasing is not a product's objective taste, but the emotional and identity-based associations a brand has cultivated over the years. Zaltman (2004), the director of the Mind Institute at Harvard University, further adds that approximately 95% of customer purchase decisions are made unconsciously. The brand has since integrated these findings into its marketing strategy, using personalised campaigns such as "Share a Coke" campaign to trigger reward systems and deepen social-emotional resonance. (Kishore & Chaithra, 2020). This phenomenon can be further explained by

Damasio's (1996) somatic marker hypothesis, which he believes is relevant to the understanding of processes of human reasoning and decision making. Damasio's key idea is that the hypothesis is that 'marker' signals, arising from bioregulatory processes including emotions and feelings, influence decision-making at multiple levels, both consciously and subconsciously. Critically, he argues that these marker signals can operate covertly; introducing biases in behavioural selection without the individual being aware of their influence. Within the context of Coca-Cola, associating the brand with happiness, togetherness, and celebration have deposited deeply embedded somatic markers in the consumers' brains. When a consumer reaches for a Coke, they aren't consciously recalling these associations, rather their prefrontal cortex retrieves the associations automatically, developing an emotional bias toward the brand before any deliberate evaluation can take place.

Nike's iconic "Just Do It" slogan offers a second case study, this time highlighting the role of 'mirror neurons' and the medial prefrontal cortex in emotional identification. Mirror neurons were first discovered and documented in macaque monkeys by Rizzolatti, Fadiga, Gallase, and Fogassi (1996), and later were applied to human marketing contexts. They are specialized brain cells that activate both when an individual performs an action and when they observe another performing the same action. When consumers view Nike adverts featuring athletes demonstrating their resilience and achievement, their mirror neuron systems fire in empathy simulation of what it is like to be one of the athletes in the bill boards (Kilner & Lemon, 2013). This mechanism pins what consumer psychologists call "aspirational identity consumption", the process by which the individual purchases products not for their utility, but as a neurological shortcut to an idealised self image. (The Science Behind Buying Decisions, 2025). Case study analysis using functional Magnetic Resonance Imaging (fMRI) and Electroencephalography (EEG) demonstrates that Nike's emotionally-charged narratives produce an increased amount of activation in the ventral striatum, and the medial prefrontal cortex, regions associated with goal-directed behaviour, self-referential processing, and social identity (Kishore & Chaithra, 2020). The result is a brand worth over \$90 billion whose value is tied not to the product features but to a neurologically reinforced sense of personal empowerment and aspiration.

The dopamine pathway is perhaps the most systematically exploited neurological mechanism in consumer marketing. Schultz (2016) established that dopamine neurons respond not only to actual rewards, but to the anticipation of reward, which fires in the nucleus accumbens and along the mesolimbic pathway whenever the brain predicts a pleasurable outcome. Marketers have ‘weaponised’ this mechanism with precision. The Starbucks Reward Program is the perfect example of the latter: customers earn points toward free items, and the anticipation of that reward constitutes the primary neurological incentives. Research on dopamine manipulation in advertising demonstrates that techniques such as scarcity cues, gamified loyalty systems, and personalised digital recommendation substantially elevate the likelihood of impulse purchases by continuously stimulating the reward system. More digital platforms such as Amazon, Instagram, and Tiktok have also followed suit with the principles, adding digital one-click purchasing, influencer-based special offers, and personalised ‘for you’ pages that are algorithmically engineered to keep the consumers on the app for longer, leading to higher likely chances of them purchasing digitally. An experimental study by Allard, 2025, found research that consistently demonstrates that influencer endorsed content significantly outperforms traditional digital advertising, with brands reporting returns of approximately 11 times higher than standard digital advertisements. This outside effectiveness is not attributable to rational product evaluation; rather, Kim et al. (2023) found that message credibility, the degree to which consumers emotionally trust the endorser, acts as the primary driver of positive consumer attitudes toward influencer-endorsed products. Together these findings suggest that influencer marketing succeeds standard digital marketing advertisements, because it resonates emotionally with the targeted audience, producing purchasing behaviour consistent with System 1, which is fast and emotional decision making, rather than deliberative, rational evaluations of the product (Kahneman, 2011).

Taken together, these case studies demonstrate that leading brands are not merely responding to consumer preferences, rather they are neurologically shaping them, even us. By targeting the limbic system’s emotional memory through brand identity, leveraging mirror neurons to create empathetic self-identification, and engineering dopamine anticipation through reward and scarcity mechanics, companies have effectively built ecosystems that operate silently below the level of consciousness of consumers' awareness. The prefrontal

cortex is bypassed not through deceptions, but through the prior and more rapid activation of emotional brain structures, meaning that by the time the consumer has consciously evaluated the purchase, the emotional decision has already been made (Zaltman, 2004).

Conclusion

The convergence of neuroscience and consumer marketing represents one of the most significant exemplar shifts in the history of marketing. This paper examined how the limbic system and the prefrontal cortex plays a huge role in purchasing contexts, how mirror neurons facilitate emotional identification between consumers and brands, and how dopamine pathways create neurologically reinforced cycles of anticipation, reward, and loyalty. The evidence drawn from both experimental neuroscience and real world brand applications, including Coca-Cola identity experiment findings, Nike's mirror neuron-driven aspiration model, and Starbucks' dopamine reward architecture; consistently supports the central thesis that purchasing decisions are predominantly emotional in nature, shaped by subconsciously purchasing decisions rather than rational cost-benefit analysis.

The implications of these findings extend beyond academic interest. For consumers, an awareness of what they're doing subconsciously offers a degree of cognitive protection against manipulation from corporations, enabling more deliberate engagement and evaluation with emotional triggers embedded in modern advertising. For marketers, the listed evidence in this paper presents an opportunity and ethical responsibility: the same neurological tools that can build authentic, lasting consumer relationships can also be deployed to exploit cognitive vulnerabilities, especially in populations with control disorders.

However, future research should address several limitations of current research. The majority of neuromarketing case studies involve large, well-resourced brands whose results of samples may not generalise across the globe, for product categories, cultures, or demographic groups. Additionally, Zaltman's research figure of 95% unconscious decision making is widely reliable, it remains difficult to verify with precision and should be interpreted with caution.

Acknowledgements

The author would like to thank Iaseer Ahmed Sobhan for inspiring the initial research direction and providing assistance with source identifications and research questions during the early stages of this project. He had significantly contributed towards the research in this project. The author would also like to acknowledge and thank Mr Craig Stuart Conlon, HS English and AP Seminar teacher at GEMS Dubai American Academy, for his guidance and willingness to be our supervisor throughout the writing process.

References

Welcome To Zscaler Directory Authentication. (2025). Acr-Journal.com.

<https://acr-journal.com/article/the-dopamine-economy-how-neuro-marketing-shapes-impulse-buying-in-digital-spaces-1197/>

Kenning, P., Plassmann, H., & Ahlert, D. (2007). Applications of functional magnetic resonance imaging for market research. *Qualitative Market Research: An International Journal*, 10(2), 135–152.

<https://doi.org/10.1108/13522750710740817>

Kilner, J. M., & Lemon, R. N. (2013). What We Know Currently about Mirror Neurons. *Current Biology*, 23(23), R1057–R1062. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cub.2013.10.051>

Padia, J. (2025). Neurons said, Yes! : A Case Study Analysis on Brands Optimizing Neuroscience as a for Strategic Marketing Tool. *Journal of Informatics Education and Research*, 5(2).

<https://doi.org/10.52783/jier.v5i2.2582>

Morin, C. (2011). Neuromarketing: The New Science of Consumer Behavior. *Society*, 48(2), 131–135.

springer. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12115-010-9408-1>

Rizzolatti, G., Fadiga, L., Gallese, V., & Fogassi, L. (1996). Premotor cortex and the recognition of motor actions. *Cognitive Brain Research*, 3(2), 131–141. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0926-6410\(95\)00038-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0926-6410(95)00038-0)

Schultz, W. (2016). Dopamine reward prediction-error signalling: a two-component response. *Nature Reviews Neuroscience*, 17(3), 183–195. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nrn.2015.26>

Zaltman, G. (2004). How customers think: Essential insights into the mind of the market. Harvard Business School Press.

<https://www.inc.com/logan-chierotti/harvard-professor-says-95-of-purchasing-decisions-are-subconscious.html>

Kim, E., Kim, D., E, Z., & Shoenberger, H. (2023). The next hype in social media advertising: Examining virtual influencers' brand endorsement effectiveness. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 14, 1089051.

<https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2023.1089051>

IQFluence. (2025). *60 vital influencer marketing statistics for your 2026*.

<https://iqfluence.io/blog/influencer-marketing-statistics>

Kahneman, D. (2011). *Thinking, fast and slow*. Psycnet.apa.org.

<https://psycnet.apa.org/record/2011-26535-000>

Damasio, A. (1996). The somatic marker hypothesis and the possible functions of the prefrontal cortex.

Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society of London. Series B: Biological Sciences, 351(1346),

1413–1420. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.1996.0125>

Consumer Psychology: The Science Behind Buying Decisions. (2025). Early Years TV.

<https://www.earlyyears.tv/consumer-psychology-science-behind-decisions/>

